

Golconda Cotton Dyeing and the Dutch East India Company: An Account from Dutch Telugu Grant of 1720 CE

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ABSTRACT

The most important part of the economy of the Golconda kingdom was its textile industry. The chief centre of this industry was Masulipatnam which was also the principal port of the kingdom from where Golconda fabrics went all over the world and established a unique reputation for quality and finish. Historically, the coast of Andhra was known for its multicoloured weaving like *kalamkari*, *chintz*, *calicoes*, etc from places like Masulipatnam, Palakollu, Narsapur, Nizampatnam and Pulicat. These textiles attracted the European companies – English, French and Dutch in particular who established their settlements at these port cities. During the first half of the 17th century they remained too involved with the spice trade of the Malaya Archipelago, for which Indian textiles constituted the staple article of barter. Nutmeg, mace and cloves, in which Indonesia possessed a monopoly, were bartered in exchange for these textiles. The research paper titled “Golconda Cotton Dyeing and the Dutch East India Company: An Account from Dutch Telugu Grant of 1720 CE” brings to light a Telugu grant issued by the Dutch which showcases the categories of textiles in which the Dutch conducted their business.

Key Words: Golconda kingdom, Economy, Textiles, Dutch Telugu Grant, East India Company

Introduction

The coastal region between the estuaries of the rivers Godavari and Cauvery was considered as an important area for the manufacture of textiles throughout the eighteenth century. Historically, the coast of Andhra was known for its multicoloured weaving.¹ The Nizampatnam region produced the best madder² on the entire coast.³ In addition to coloured woven textiles, the Chirala region also produced *ikat*, a unique type of fabric.⁴ The term *ikat* refers to a kind of fabrics made from yarn that was tied and resisted before being dyed, leaving an imprint of the design on the yarn before it was threaded through the loom. There was no tradition of *ikat* in the Tamil Nadu area and the coastal area here was better known for its fine *kalamkari* variety.⁵ The woven items from Andhra Pradesh's coast and the *kalamkari* fabrics from Tamil Nadu's coast played a significant role in the spice trade. Nutmeg, mace and cloves, in which Indonesia possessed a monopoly, were bartered in exchange for these textiles.⁶ The geography of the area was understood by European traders in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries. The internal territory received recognition as Carnatic, while the coastal region from Nagapatnam to the river Krishna was referred to as Coromandel. The Gingelly Coast was the name given to the coastal region between the Krishna and Godavari rivers.⁷

Golconda Cotton Dyeing and the Dutch East India Company:

Craft traditions may have stayed distinct because political mastery traditions in the two units had been so dissimilar. The Cholas had a significant impact on the southern region. When the port town of Motupalli attracted a lot of mercantile industry, the Kakatiyas and Reddis had fostered the northern unit.⁸ When the Bahmani Kingdom was established, with Gulbarga as its capital, trade activity tended to transfer to ports along the west coast, like Goa.⁹ The eastern exits were given new life when the Persianized Qutb Shahi¹⁰ Sultanate was created at Golconda, with the port city of Masulipatam¹¹ filling the role that had previously fallen to Motupalli.

The southern unit also received a significant boost from Vijayanagar. Although the *kalamkari* technique was reportedly used in the second century of the Christian era¹², nothing is known about the styles that were popular at the time or the creators' identities. The mural paintings of the Virupaksha Temple in Hampi may be linked to the ornamental style in the other instances of seventeenth-century *kalamkari* made in the southern sector. With the

immigration of Telugu speakers into Tamil land, Vijayanagar suzerainty was also accompanied by a degree of demographic shift. Now, members of the Telugu Naidu group started to control the painting of *kalamkari* goods exclusively.¹³

With the emergence of Qutb Shahi control, former trade routes were once again open in the northern region. A demand was formed outside of the Spice Islands in the Red Sea markets, particularly in Iran, which was then known as Persia.¹⁴ As a result, a new line of textiles was created. The production of *kalamkari* ceramics on a large scale started. The Persian market was strong, and fashion trends frequently matched customer tastes. The painters of *kalamkari* were chosen from the Naidu community, same like in the Tamil Nadu region. Although the *kalamkari* tradition was far more deeply ingrained in the Tamil Nadu region, the painted goods of the Golconda coast quickly gained a reputation for greater quality, probably as a result of court sponsorship. John Irwin and K.B. Brett gave the term ‘early Coromandel’ to the textiles connected to the Coromandel and Gingelly beaches. The Gingelly coast and the Coromandel are represented by the Golconda School and Madras-Pulicat School, respectively, in the further subdivision of these textiles.¹⁵

The Motupalli charter¹⁶ and the opulent activities of Raja Chola and Rajendra Chola¹⁷ hint at an indigenous nautical heritage that was carried out on a significant scale, but the specifics of local maritime expertise are still unknown. The *Chettians* played a part in the south when the Europeans arrived, and Masulipatam’s early history has been linked to the existence of an Arab town.¹⁸ Europeans were drawn to the east coast as a result of their involvement in the spice trade. In Golconda, the Dutch were in an especially advantageous position. In addition to having significant advantages in the spice trade, they were the only Europeans who were allowed to live in Japan. They were able to enter Golconda with Japanese gold and copper because to this. The Dutch had an advantage over other European competitors in the Persian market thanks to the same benefit. Although the Dutch themselves were more interested in Persian silk than in Golconda painted cottons, they were fully aware of this additional aspect of Persian demand.¹⁹ Masulipatam (1605), Petapoly (1605), Palakollu (1606), Golconda (1661), as well as Datcheron, Nagalwanse, and Bimlipatam were among the Dutch outposts in Golconda.²⁰

Finding and conclusion:

Despite the fact that in present times almost all traces of *kalamakari* activity and Dutch presence have been wiped out from Palakollu, the discovery of a document issued by the Dutch V.O.C. (*Vereenigde Oost Indische Compagnie*) in the possession of a long-established family of cotton painters has come as a surprise. The Dutch administration issued the grant for Chittaravu tank on 25 February, 1720 CE from Palakollu.

Dutch Company Document in Telugu, 1720 CE

The English translation reads as follows:

Sri Rama Sankara with the agreement of Gharatu Vestinam and having consulted the opperkapu²¹ of the eastern region, the present document has been drafted. The following has been written by Rajadri Kapu Manu (head farmer)²² in the name of Colonel Bodivense. Bukru Buru was the karrani (accountant), John Hales was the head writer, Abraham Punde Kustali was under-writer. This paper was addressed by the head of the Company to Kondepudi Atchanna. You had requested us for the grant of two kattula²³ of land. You had wished to construct a tank on this so that you could speed up the rate of your delivery to the Company and dye many saris (kokkalu) required by the Company. We wrote to the Governor of Nagapatam and secured his sanction. You have been granted two kattula of land to the south of Mochupalle village inclusive of Chittaravu tank. You may construct a tank and utilise the water of Chittaravu tank for the dyeing of saris. This land is granted to you and your successors to earn your livelihood. You can feed your tank with the waters of the river Veddava running to the south of the tank.

The document, which was written in Telugu rather than Persian, is really interesting. Since it was given to members of the Naidu community, the oral tradition connecting this group to the occupation of cotton painting and dyeing was strengthened. The fact that such a document was published in the year 1720 substantiates to the evidence that, by that year, cotton textile production had significantly recovered from the devastating famine of 1686-1687, which had brought it to a virtual halt.²⁴ This was definitely aided by the stern rule of Mubariz Khan, the Mughal governor of Hyderabad from 1713 to 1724 CE. Masulipatam, which had endured much hardship following the fall of Golconda in 1687, was actually in such a prosperous state by the year 1723 that the English merchant Humphrey Holcombe, who had been sent to reopen the Company counter there, complained that there was so much demand that labour had become scarce and expensive.²⁵ It seems a little odd that the Dutch, who only sold their products on the outside market, would order *kokkalu* (saris), but it's possible that the Telugu draughtsman used the colloquial term because he wasn't fully familiar with the full range of trade terms relating to the specific categories of textiles in which the Dutch conducted their business.

¹ See S.P. Reddi, Hindi Trans. from original in Telugu by R.V. Rao, *Andhra ka Samajik Itihas*, Sahitya Akademi, New Delhi, 1959, pp.13, 78, 147, 314; M.S.Sarma, *History of the Reddi Kingdoms*, Waltair, 1948, pp.285, 288; A.V. Krishnamoorthy, *Social and Economic Conditions in Eastern Deccan, CE. 1000-1250*, Secunderabad, 1970, p.57; J. Parker, ed., *Merchants and Scholars*, Minneapolis, 1965, Burton Stein, “Coromandel Trade in Medieval India”, p.52; J.J. Brenning, *The Textile Trade of Seventeenth Century Northern Cormandel; A Study of Pre-Modern Asia Export Industry*, unpublished Ph.D. dissertation, University of Wisconsin, 1975, p.227.

² *Rubia tinctorum*, the rose madder or common madder or dyer’s madder is a plant variety which has been used since ancient times as a vegetable red dye for leather, wool, cotton and silk.

³ W.H.Moreland, *Relations of Golconda in the Early Seventeenth Century* (henceforth cited as *Relations*), London, 1931, pp.54-55. Earlier it had been known as Arjumptnam while the English referred to it as Pettikpoly. *Indian Historical Quarterly*, 1941, Srinivasachari, p.240.

⁴ B.C. Mohanty and Kalyan Krishna (*Ikat Fabrics of Orissa and Andhra Pradesh*, Ahmadabad, 1974, p. 21) are of view that *ikat* tradition in Andhra is a very late one. However, linkage with *ikat* tradition at Jalna suggests a much older origin. See *ibid.*, p. 15; *Journal of Indian Textile History*, No.1, 1955, Pupul Jayakar, “A Neglected Group of Indian Ikat Fabrics” pp.55, 57-58.

⁵ For the connotation of the term, *kalamkari*, see *Homage to Kalamkari*, Marg Publications, Bombay, 1979; Lotika Varadarajan, “Towards a Definition of *Kalamkari*”, pp.19-21. For *Kalamkari* in Tamil Nadu see W.H. Moreland, *From Akbar to Aurangzeb*, Delhi, 1972 (reprint, London edition of 1923), p.32; J. Macau, *L’Inde Danoise, La Premiere Compagnie (1616-1670)*, Et udes et Documents, No 3, Institut d’ Histoire des Fays d’Outre Mer, Aix-en-Provcnce, pp.29, 105-106.

⁶ For the exchange ratios between textiles and spices see G.P. Rouffaer, H.H. Juynball, *De Batik-Kunst ill Nederlandsch-Indie en Haar Gaschiedenis*, Utrecht, 1913, Bijlage (Appendix) III.

⁷ J.J. Brenning, *op.cit.*, p.5; Burton Stein (J. Parker, *op.cit.*, article cited by Burton Stein, p. 60. no. I) defines the Coromandel as the coastal stretch of eastern peninsula India extending from Cape Comorin to the mouth of the river Godavari in modern Andhra Pradesh.

⁸ See S.P. Rccdi, *op.cit.*, pp. 84, 142; M.S. Sarma, *op. cit.*, pp. 403.405.

⁹ J.J. Brenning, *op.cit.*, pp.15-19.

¹⁰ For the origin of this dynasty see *Itihas*, III, 1975, Ziauddin Ahmed Shakeb, “The Black Sheep Tribe from Lake Van to Golconda”, pp.35-66.

¹¹ For early references to Masulipatam see *Krishna District Gazetteer*, March 1968, draft copy at State Archives, Hyderabad, p.43. Variations in the European spelling of Masulipatam are discussed by R.C. Temple, *Indian Antiquary*, XXX, “Extracts from the log book of a voyage along the coast of India in 1746”, p.348). Thomas Bowrey records that during the period 1669-1679 Masulipatnam served as an outlet for an area extending one hundred miles in circuit. T. Bowrey, *A Geographical Account of Countries Round the Bay of Bengal, 1669-1679*, Cambridge, 1905, p.105.

¹² See Lotika Varadarjan, *South Indian Traditions of Kalamkari*, Cyclostyled copy at National Institute of Design, Ahmadabad, p.11.

¹³ This observation is based on oral tradition collated in the course of extensive field work undertaken by the author in coastal Andhra Pradesh, Kalahasti and Kumbakonam in areas where *Kalamkari* is still being practiced. Cr. *Lalit Kala*, No. 5, 1959, John Irwin, “Golconda Cotton Paintings of the Early Seventeenth Century”, p.20, n.3.

¹⁴ S.P. Reddi (*op.cit.*, pp.84, 142, 144-146) and M.S. Sarma (*op.cit.*, pp.403-405), describe the wide ambit of commercial transactions during the Kakatiya and Reddi periods conducted through the port of Motupalli. The

channels of trade extended to Hormuz, Ceylon, Malaya, Sumatra and China. Under the Bahmanis there was a decline and this may account for the fact noted by the Dutch traveller Schorer that the Qutb Shahis came to power there were no trade links in existence between Masulipatnam and the markets of the Red Sea or the Spice Islands. See J.J. Brenning, *op.cit.*, pp.21-22. For the links between Golconda and Persia See *Islamic Culture* (hence forth I.C.), XXXIII, 1959, M. Alam, p.1781; John Irwin, K.B. Brett, *Origins of Chintz*, London, 1970, p. 13.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, *op.cit.*

¹⁶ See M.S. Sarma, *op.cit.*, pp.404-405.

¹⁷ See Nilakanta Shastri, *A History of South India*, 4th edition, Madras, 1976, pp.182,184.

¹⁸ See G. Mackenzie, *A Manual of Krishna District in the Presidency of Madras*, 1883, p.87.

¹⁹ See I.C., XXXIII, 1959, M. Alam, pp.172, 175-176, 178-179; P.M. Joshi, M.A. Nayeem eds., *Studies in the Foreign Relations of India*, State Archives, Hyderabad, 1975, Lotika Varadarajan, "Foreign Trade of Surat 1650-1700", pp.481-482.

²⁰ For further details relating to these counters see W.H. Moreland, *Relations*, p.61, n 2; J.J. Brenning, *op.cit.* pp.24-25;125; B.B. Kling, M.N. Pearson, eds., *Age of Partnership*, Honolulu, 1979, p.94 n.1; *Bulletin de l'Ecole Francaise d'Extreme Orient*, LXII, 1975, J. Deloche, "Le Memor de Morocians sur Macilipattanamu; Un Tableau des Conditions Economiques et Sociales des Provinces Cotieres de l' Andhra au Milieu du XVIII siecle" p.10.

²¹ The term is associated with the caste of tank diggers. However, an alternative meaning is possible as Dutch administrative hierarchy included an official known as *Opporkoopman* or Senior Merchant. See *Ceylon Journal of Historical and Social Studies*, 8, 1965, S. Arasaratnam, "The administrative organisation of the Dutch Company in Ceylon", p.2.

²² The practice of revenue farming known as chuda-dari was a well accepted one in Qutb Shahi Golconda. See T. Raychaudhuri, *Jan Company in the Coromandel*, The Hague, 1962, p.7. Although frowned upon, it existed under the name *ijara* in the Mughal Empire. M. Athar Ali, *The Mughal Nobility under Aurangzeb*, Bombay, 1970 (reprint), pp.83-84. When Golconda was absorbed into the Mughal empire, attempts were made to root-out revenue farming but these efforts culminated in only a limited measure of success. See J.F. Richards, *Mughal Administration in Golconda*, Oxford University Press, 1975, pp.169, 172, 212-213.

²³ According to Shri M.A. Haq, the *kattula* was a variable unit of land measurement. He pointed out that in Government records it was rated at 40 acres and 14 *kuntas*. See also H.H. Wilson, *A Glossary of Judicial and Revenue Terms*, Delhi, 1968 (Reprint of London 1855 edition), *Kathi, Katlai* q.v.

²⁴ J.F. Richards, *op.cit.*, pp. 69-70.

²⁵ *Ibid.*, p.304.